

Studies on Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) Complexes with 2-Substituted-benzimidazoles

N. SHASHIKALA, N. M. NANJE GOWDA and G. K. N. REDDY*

Department of Chemistry, Central College, Bangalore University, Bangalore-560 001

Nickel(II) halides and palladium(II) halides react with 2-substituted-benzimidazoles to give complexes of the formula MX_2L_2 , where $\text{M}=\text{Ni}$; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{L}=\text{EtBzIH}, n\text{-PrBzIH}, i\text{-PrBzIH}, \text{AmPhBzIH}, \text{FuBzIH}$; $\text{M}=\text{Pd}$; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{L}=\text{EtBzIH}, n\text{-PrBzIH}, i\text{-PrBzIH}, n\text{-BuBzIH}$. Magnetic susceptibility measurements, ir and electronic spectral studies suggest that complexes of nickel containing alkylbenzimidazoles possess a tetrahedral stereochemistry, while those with AmPhBzIH and FuBzIH have octahedral and square-pyramidal geometries, respectively. A square-planar geometry has been suggested for the palladium complexes.

CONSIDERABLE attention is being paid in recent years to the study of transition metal complexes of imidazoles, benzimidazoles and related ligands because of their biological significance and interesting spectral, magnetic and structural aspects¹⁻⁵. We have reported earlier⁶ the isolation and characterisation of complexes of cobalt(II) with 2-substituted-benzimidazoles. A similar study of nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes is being reported here. A few such complexes have, however, been reported earlier by other workers⁷⁻¹².

Experimental

Nickel halides ($\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NiBr}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were from B.D.H. Palladium chloride was supplied by Johnson Matthey. The 2-substituted benzimidazole ligands were prepared according to the literature methods^{13,14}. The infrared (nujol) and solid state and solution electronic spectra were recorded on Carl-Zeiss SPECORD 75 IR and DMR 21 UV-VIS-NIR and Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometers, respectively. Magnetic moments were measured with a Gouy balance. Conductivity measurements were made with a Toshniwal CL 01.02 conductivity bridge.

Dihalobis(2-alkylbenzimidazole)nickel(II) complexes (NiX_2L_2 ; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{L}=\text{EtBzIH}, n\text{-PrBzIH}, i\text{-PrBzIH}$): A solution of nickel(II) halide hexahydrate (1 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) was dehydrated by the addition of triethylorthoformate (TEOF; 5 ml) at refluxing temperature. To it was added 2-alkylbenzimidazole (2 mmol) in ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for about 4 h. The resultant mixture was concentrated to a small volume under reduced pressure and was left overnight during which blue crystals separated. The crystals were washed with ethanol-TEOF mixture and dried *in vacuo*.

Dihalobis(2-o-aminophenyl/2-furylbenzimidazole)-nickel(II) complexes (NiX_2L_2 ; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{L}=\text{AmPhBzIH}, \text{FuBzIH}$): To a solution of nickel(II) halide hexahydrate (1 mmol) in ethanol-TEOF (15 ml; 2:1) was added the 2-substituted benzimidazole (2 mmol) in ethanol (5 ml). On refluxing the mixture for nearly 3 h, green or greenish blue compound separated, which was washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Dihalobis(2-alkylbenzimidazole)palladium(II) complexes (PdX_2L_2 ; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{L}=\text{EtBzIH}, n\text{-PrBzIH}, i\text{-PrBzIH}, n\text{-BuBzIH}$): Palladium halide (1 mmol) dissolved in hydrohalic acid (0.5 ml) was treated with 2-alkylbenzimidazole (2 mmol) in acetone (10 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for about 4 h. The solution was concentrated to a small volume under reduced pressure, when the desired product got separated. The product was washed successively with water and acetone and dried. The solid was recrystallised from ethanol.

Results and Discussion

Nickel(II) halides react with 2-substituted-benzimidazoles (2-R-BzIH; R=ethyl (Et), propyl (Pr), aminophenyl (AmPh), furyl (Fu)) in the mole ratio 1:2 in neutral ethanolic medium in presence of the dehydrating agent TEOF to form blue to green complexes of the formula NiX_2L_2 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{L}=\text{EtBzIH}, n\text{-PrBzIH}, i\text{-PrBzIH}, \text{AmPhBzIH}, \text{FuBzIH}$). In the absence of TEOF, the products could not be isolated in a pure state. Palladium halides react with 2-substituted benzimidazoles in acetone to produce yellow complexes of the composition PdX_2L_2 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{L}=\text{EtBzIH}, n\text{-PrBzIH}, i\text{-PrBzIH}, n\text{-BuBzIH}$). All the complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The analytical data along with some physical data of the complexes are collected in Table I.

The nickel(II) complexes containing 2-alkyl substituted benzimidazoles are soluble in common organic solvents and show low conductivity in

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF NICKEL(II) AND PALLADIUM(II) COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p./Dec.p. °C	Λ^a	μ_{eff} (at 298 K) B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
NiCl ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂	224	25 ^b	3.45	51.0 (51.2)	4.5 (4.8)	18.0 (18.8)
NiBr ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂	246-48	55 ^b	3.51	42.1 (42.3)	3.9 (4.0)	10.7 (11.0)
NiCl ₂ (n-PrBz1H) ₂	241-43	92 ^b	3.55	53.1 (53.4)	5.3 (5.4)	11.9 (12.4)
NiBr ₂ (n-PrBz1H) ₂	242-43	48 ^b	—	45.0 (44.6)	4.4 (4.5)	10.1 (10.4)
NiCl ₂ (i-PrBz1H) ₂	>250	39 ^b	3.47	53.0 (53.4)	5.3 (5.4)	11.8 (12.4)
NiBr ₂ (i-PrBz1H) ₂	>250	54 ^b	3.49	44.1 (44.6)	4.2 (4.5)	9.8 (10.4)
NiCl ₂ (AmPhBz1H) ₂	>250	39	3.20	57.0 (57.0)	4.1 (4.0)	15.9 (15.8)
NiBr ₂ (AmPhBz1H) ₂	>250	102	3.33	48.9 (49.0)	3.5 (3.5)	13.0 (13.2)
NiCl ₂ (FuBz1H) ₂	>250	45	3.35	52.0 (53.1)	3.5 (3.2)	11.5 (11.3)
NiBr ₂ (FuBz1H) ₂	>250	113	3.20	45.1 (45.0)	3.2 (2.8)	9.7 (9.5)
PdCl ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂	180	6	—	45.2 (46.0)	4.8 (4.3)	11.1 (11.9)
PdBr ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂	230	8	—	39.5 (38.7)	3.4 (3.6)	9.6 (10.0)
PdCl ₂ (n-PrBz1H) ₂	>250	8	—	47.9 (48.3)	4.8 (4.9)	11.0 (11.3)
PdBr ₂ (n-PrBz1H) ₂	110	8	—	40.1 (41.0)	4.1 (4.1)	9.4 (9.6)
PdCl ₂ (i-PrBz1H) ₂	210-12	7	—	47.4 (48.3)	4.8 (4.9)	11.0 (11.3)
PdBr ₂ (i-PrBz1H) ₂	180-85	6	—	40.2 (41.0)	4.1 (4.1)	9.8 (9.6)
PdCl ₂ (n-BuBz1H) ₂	>250	5	—	50.4 (50.3)	5.1 (5.4)	10.4 (10.7)
PdBr ₂ (n-BuBz1H) ₂	>250	6	—	42.5 (43.0)	4.5 (4.6)	8.9 (9.1)

^a Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of $\sim 10^{-3} M$ solutions around 25° in DMF.^b In acetonitrile.

acetonitrile. The AmPhBz1H and FuBz1H containing complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but dissolve in dimethylformamide (DMF) to give solutions that show appreciable conductivity. We believe that the low and appreciable conductivity, respectively of these complexes in acetonitrile and DMF is due to equilibria of the type

in solution. The conductivity values^{1,5} appear to indicate that the bromides ionise to a greater extent than the chlorides in solution. The palladium complexes are insoluble in organic solvents except DMF in which they are non-electrolytes.

Magnetic susceptibility : The room temperature magnetic susceptibilities for the complexes NiX₂L₂ (X = Cl, Br ; L = EtBz1H, n-PrBz1H, i-PrBz1H) have been measured and the calculated moments are in the range 3.4-3.6 B.M. (Table 1). The moments are in the right range expected for tetrahedral

stereochemistry of the complexes. On the other hand, the magnetic moment values of AmPhBz1H and FuBz1H complexes of nickel(II) are in the range 3.20-3.35 B.M. These values fall in the range expected for octahedral or distorted octahedral stereochemistry for the complexes^{1,6}.

Infrared spectra : The nujol mull infrared spectra of the ligands except that of aminophenyl benzimidazole do not show the expected $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ band in the 3 500-3 200 cm^{-1} region presumably due to inter-ligand hydrogen bonding. However, dichloromethane solutions of the ligands show a strong and sharp peak around 3 440 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ indicating the breakdown of hydrogen bonding in solution^{1,7}. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ vibrations are very close and occur around 1 625 cm^{-1} as weak bands. The N-H in-plane bending appears around 1 590 cm^{-1} , while the band appearing at 1 540 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ vibrations. $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\delta_{\text{N-H}}$ appear around 1 320 cm^{-1} . The bands around 1 410, 1 275, 1 000, 740, 615 and 430 cm^{-1} are assigned to ring vibrations. A weak band appears around 780 cm^{-1} and is ascribed to N-H out-of-plane bending vibration. These band assign-

ments are tentative and have been made on the basis of similar assignments made in the case of benzimidazole and 2- α -pyridylbenzimidazole¹⁸⁻²⁰.

The infrared spectrum of 2-*o*-aminophenylbenzimidazole shows two bands, one at 3 380 cm⁻¹ and another split band at 3 160 and 3 130 cm⁻¹. The former has been assigned to the ν_{N-H} of NH₂ of the phenyl ring and the latter to the ν_{N-H} of the benzimidazole ring. A shoulder at 1 625 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to ν_{C-N} . The band at 1 615 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the NH₂ in-plane bending mode. The *ortho*-substituted phenyl group shows ring vibrations at 1 485 and 745 cm⁻¹. A band at 1 040 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{C-N} of the aminophenyl group and another at 855 cm⁻¹ to the NH₂ out-of-plane bending vibration. The other bands in the spectrum due to the benzimidazole moiety appear more or less at the same positions as in the 2-alkyl-substituted-benzimidazoles. The spectrum of 2,2'-furylbenzimidazole is also similar to the spectra of the 2-alkylbenzimidazoles except that there are a few additional bands due to the furan ring. Thus, the band occurring at 1 240 cm⁻¹ is probably due to ν_{C-O} and a band at 885 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of the presence of furan group^{18,21-23}. The C-H out-of-plane bending of furan moiety may have been obscured in the benzimidazole ring vibration at 740 cm⁻¹.

The infrared spectra of the NiX₂L₂ and PdX₂L₂ complexes are similar to those of the corresponding ligands. The N-H stretching vibration which is absent in the spectra of the ligands due to inter-ligand hydrogen bonding, appears in the 3 200-3 100 cm⁻¹ region in the spectra of the complexes and has a considerably lower value as compared to that for the free ligand. The other bands in the spectrum of each complex are similar to those in the corresponding ligand spectrum except for slight shifts in their positions and changes in their intensities due to coordination.

Electronic spectra: The solid state electronic spectra of NiX₂L₂ complexes (X=Cl, Br; L=EtBz1H, *n*-PrBz1H, *i*-PrBz1H) were taken in nujol mull in the region 30 000 to 4 000 cm⁻¹ and the data have been listed in Table 2. These spectral results are very useful in assigning the stereochemistry of the complexes and for calculating the

ligand field parameters. The complexes are intense blue in colour and show three absorption bands around 7 000, 10 000 and a split band in the region 15 000-18 000 cm⁻¹. The low energy location of the bands and their high intensities suggest a tetrahedral configuration for the complexes. The observed bands may be assigned to the transitions ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_2(\nu_1)$; ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3A_2(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)(\nu_3)$, respectively. The spectra of the complexes also show a very weak band around 12 000 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to the forbidden transition ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^1E^{24}$. The ligand field parameters 10Dq, Racah parameter (B') and nephelauxetic parameter (β) have been calculated (Table 2) using the frequency values corresponding to the centre of gravity of the ν_2 and ν_3 (split) absorption bands and following the method of Underhill and Billing²⁵.

The electronic spectra of the above nickel(II) complexes and those of the corresponding ligands have also been taken in acetonitrile in the region 50 000 to 11 200 cm⁻¹ (Table 3). The ligands show three prominent bands around 46 000, 40 000 and 36 000 cm⁻¹ (split). The former two bands arise due to the imidazole moiety and the latter due to benzene ring of the ligand^{19,26}; the splitting of this band may be due to lowering of the symmetry of the benzene ring. The complexes exhibit very intense bands in the uv region and a very weak broad band in the visible region around 16 000 cm⁻¹. The positions and the features of the bands in the uv region are nearly the same as those of the ligand bands. The band in the visible region may be ascribed to the ν_3 transition, *i.e.* ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ due to tetrahedral stereochemistry of the complexes.

The nujol mull spectra (taken in the region 50 000 to 11 200 cm⁻¹) of NiX₂(AmPhBz1H)₂ complexes show absorption bands around 16 000 and 25 000 cm⁻¹. The positions and the low intensities of the bands suggest an octahedral geometry for the complexes. The low energy band may be assigned to the ν_2 transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and the high energy band may be ascribed to the ν_3 transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$. The uv region of the spectra is not well resolved and is not useful to recognise any meaningful band. The electronic spectra of AmPhBz1H and NiX₂(AmPhBz1H)₂ complexes have also been taken in DMF solution.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (NUJOL; cm⁻¹) FOR NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES^a

Compd.	ν_1	ν_2	ν^b	ν_3	10Dq	B'	β
NiCl ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂	7 174	10 121	13 483	15 625, 18 248	5 468	873	0.84
NiBr ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂	6 802	9 960	11 745	14 749, 17 794	5 154	787	0.76
NiCl ₂ (<i>n</i> -PrBz1H) ₂	6 793	9 940	13 457	15 625, 17 921	5 365	869	0.83
NiBr ₂ (<i>n</i> -PrBz1H) ₂	6 766	9 728	—	15 198, 17 483	5 172	827	0.79
NiCl ₂ (<i>i</i> -PrBz1H) ₂	6 964	10 000	13 439	15 576, 17 987	5 398	859	0.82
NiBr ₂ (<i>i</i> -PrBz1H) ₂	6 944	9 881	11 738	14 793, 17 361	5 331	826	0.79

^a ν_1 and ν_2 bands broad; ν_3 bands are strong; B, taken to be 1 041 cm⁻¹ for nickel(II) free ion. ^b ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^1E$.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) FOR NICKEL(II) AND PALLADIUM(II) COMPLEXES

Compd.	Nujol	$\bar{\nu}$ (e)	CH ₂ ON
EtBz1H		35 549(6 848), 36 430(7 429), 40 634(7 537) 46 685(9 592)	
NiCl ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂		16 132(199), 17 575(247), 35 689(7 213), 36 403(9 551), 36 996(9 047), 40 967(11 007) 46 168(9 241)	
NiBr ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂		15 193(74), 17 144(87), 35 587(16 712) 36 417(24 432), 37 161(21 117), 40 833(21 912), 45 872(39 532)	
n-PrBz1H		35 511(8 578), 36 470(8 254), 40 601(8 625), 46 773(12 189)	
NiCl ₂ (n-PrBz1H) ₂		16 062(89), 17 476(106), 35 613(24 501), 36 688(29 001), 36 928(25 897), 40 900(33 189) 46 019(26 577)	
NiBr ₂ (n-PrBz1H) ₂		15 281(87), 17 091(109), 35 612(21 093), 36 390(25 250), 36 982(21 728), 40 650(24 596), 45 683(35 547)	
i-PrBz1H		35 537(8 025), 36 417(8 590), 40 717(8 963), 46 404(9 276)	
NiCl ₂ (i-PrBz1H) ₂		15 270(77), 16 305(96), 17 355(102), 35 562(21 415), 36 377(25 707), 36 955(22 476), 40 833(29 191), 46 425(29 560)	
NiBr ₂ (i-PrBz1H) ₂		14 484(26), 15 211(34), 16 952(34), 35 537(18 604), 36 350(17 785), 37 133(15 109), 40 733(16 094), 46 019(29 344)	
DMF			
AmPhBz1H		28 401(16 968), 33 356(16 204), 34 223(14 258),--- 35 625(10 461), 37 636(9 227)	
NiCl ₂ (AmPhBz1H) ₂	15 694, 25 533	14 896(7), 24 172(16), 28 482(29 435), 33 367(29 261), 34 188(26 065), 35 486(19 304), 37 779(16 391)	
NiBr ₂ (AmPhBz1H) ₂	16 667, 22 080	15 239(7), 23 810(15), 28 425(25 170), 33 389(25 538), 34 188(24 578), 35 474(19 433), 37 369(15 104)	
FuBz1H		31 066(24 727), 33 344(25 374), 32 384(26 508), 33 256(25 374), 37 594(9 436)	
NiCl ₂ (FuBz1H) ₂	14 952, 20 855, 25 445	12 984(5), 14 434(8), 16 090(7), 17 431(6), 20 674(4), 24 137(28), 31 075(42 389), 32 468(45 221) 33 167(43 680), 37 552(15 919)	
NiBr ₂ (FuBz1H) ₂	16 010, 20 784, 25 510	14 354(13), 14 741(12), 15 547(9), 16 106(6), 21 566(4), 24 624(21), 31 056(48 877), 32 489(51 635), 33 179(50 880), 37 566(18 803)	
EtBz1H		35 361(13 588), 36 232(14 120), 37 258(9 568)	
PdCl ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂	24 808	24 832(166), 35 804(11 409), 36 684(13 200), 37 425(12 287)	
PdBr ₂ (EtBz1H) ₂	23 579	23 691(254), 35 765(17 070), 36 670(19 355), 37 286(18 350)	
n-PrBz1H		35 398(5 767), 36 258(6 029), 36 928(4 689)	
PdCl ₂ (n-PrBz1H) ₂	25 170	24 863(208), 35 778(11 529), 36 670(13 225), 37 495(11 010)	
PdBr ₂ (n-PrBz1H) ₂	24 355	23 810(205), 35 804(15 646), 36 630(16 773), 37 651(15 893)	
i-PrBz1H		35 398(9 338), 36 245(10 196), 37 327(7 308)	
PdCl ₂ (i-PrBz1H) ₂	24 624	24 746(168), 35 804(13 977), 36 590(15 149), 37 425(13 008)	
PdBr ₂ (i-PrBz1H) ₂	24 096	23 691(263), 35 817(14 884), 36 697(15 933), 34 425(14 389)	
n-BuBz1H		35 386(15 530), 36 219(17 486), 37 258(12 753)	
PdCl ₂ (n-BuBz1H) ₂	25 478	24 777(150), 35 842(13 071), 36 684(13 913), 37 355(11 903)	
PdBr ₂ (n-BuBz1H) ₂	24 266	23 691(254), 35 765(14 175), 36 483(14 203), 37 355(12 793)	

The ligand spectrum shows two intense bands in the uv region around 28 000 and 35 000 cm⁻¹ (split); the former may be assigned to the amino-phenyl group and the latter may arise due to benzene rings of the AmPhBz1H. The spectra of the complexes exhibit, in addition to the ligand bands, a very weak and broad band around 15 000 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder around 24 000 cm⁻¹ in the visible region. The positions of the latter bands indicate that the octahedral geometry of the complexes is retained in solution and the bands are respectively ascribed to ν_2 and ν_3 transitions as in the case of solid state spectra²⁴.

The solid state electronic spectra (scanned in the region 50 000 to 11 200 cm⁻¹) of NiX₂(FuBz1H)₂ complexes display weak bands in the visible region around 15 000, 21 000 and 25 000 cm⁻¹, and the uv region again is not well resolved. It is noticed that the nickel(II) complex [Ni(ClO₄)(OAsMePh₂)₂] ClO₄, which has been assigned a square-pyramidal geometry, also shows bands nearly in the same region of the spectrum^{24,27}. On this basis, the FuBz1H complexes may be assigned either a distorted octahedral or a square-pyramidal geometry. In the latter geometry, the FuBz1H ligands show a bidentate behaviour and are located in the square

plane, while one of the halides is at the apical position. The spectral bands may tentatively be assigned to ${}^3B_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3E(F)$ $15\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, ${}^3B_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3A_2(P)$ $21\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and ${}^3B_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3E(P)$ $25\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The electronic spectra of the ligand FuBz1H and the corresponding $\text{NiX}_2(\text{FuBz1H})_2$ complexes have been recorded in DMF solution. The ligand shows an intense band around $33\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (split), which arises due to the benzene ring. The complexes exhibit, in addition to the ligand band, several weak bands in the visible region (Table 3). These spectral features (Fig. 1) also are characteristic of square-pyramidal geometry rather than octahedral geometry for the complexes.

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra in DMF: (a) $\text{NiCl}_2(\text{FuBz1H})_2$, and (b) $\text{NiBr}_2(\text{FuBz1H})_2$.

The solid state electronic spectra (in the region $50\,000$ to $11\,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of palladium(II) complexes have also been taken in nujol and the spectra show a weak band in the region $24\,000$ – $25\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 3). This band may be assigned to the ν_1 transition ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ arising from a square-planar stereochemistry for the complexes. The position of the band is comparable to those reported earlier for square-planar complexes of palladium(II)^{13,23,29}. In the uv region, an intense very broad band with a maximum around $35\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed and this may arise due to overlap of bands arising from imidazole moiety and benzene ring of the benzimidazole ligand. The electronic spectra of the palladium complexes and the corresponding ligands have also been taken in DMF. The free ligands

show a strong band around $36\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (split) and this band may be due to benzene ring of the benzimidazole derivative. The complexes also show in addition to the above strong band, a weak band around $24\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 3), which may be assigned to the ν_1 transition, i.e. ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$, due to square-planar stereochemistry of the complexes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. G. A. Webb, University of Surrey, England, for microanalyses. One of the authors (N.S.) is grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. R. J. SUNDBERG and R. B. MARTIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 74, 471.
2. P. N. PRESTON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 74, 279.
3. R. C. VAN LANDSCHOOT, J. A. M. VAN HEST and J. BREDIJK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, 38, 185.
4. L. K. THOMPSON, B. RAMASWAMY and R. D. DAWE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, 56, 1311.
5. G. K. N. REDDY and B. R. RAMESH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, 15, 621.
6. N. SHASHIKALA, E. G. LHELAMANI and G. K. N. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 743.
7. D. M. L. GOODGAME, M. GOODGAME and G. W. RAYNER CANHAM, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1972, 6, 245.
8. M. J. CABELL, D. W. CARD, R. ORZESKOWIAK and M. GOLDSTEIN, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 1687.
9. B. FIGGOTT and A. C. SKAPSKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, 77, L171.
10. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 1153.
11. L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 408.
12. M. BIDDAU, M. MASSACESI and G. PONTICELLI, *Polyhedron*, 1983, 2, 1261.
13. D. W. HEIN, R. I. ALHURN and J. J. LIGUITT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 427.
14. Y. KANAWKA, O. YONEMITSU, K. TANIZAWA and Y. BAN, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1964, 12, 773.
15. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.
16. B. N. FIGGIS, 'Introduction to Ligand Fields', Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1976.
17. K. J. MORGAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2343.
18. M. M. GORDES and J. W. WALTER, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1968, 24, 1421.
19. D. J. RABIGER and M. M. JOULLIER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 476.
20. T. J. LANE, C. S. C. I. NAKAGAWA, J. L. WALTER, C. S. C. and A. J. KANDATHI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 267.
21. K. NAKANISHI and P. H. SOLOMON, 'Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy', Holden-Day, Sydney, 1977.
22. L. J. BELLAMY, 'The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules', John Wiley, New York, 1962.
23. N. S. BIRADAR and T. R. GOUDAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 358.
24. A. B. P. LEVIER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy', Elsevier, New York, 1968.
25. A. E. UNDERHILL and D. E. BILLING, *Nature (London)*, 1966, 210, 834.
26. C. N. R. RAO, 'Ultra-violet and Visible Spectroscopy', 3rd ed., Butterworth, and Co. Ltd., 1975.
27. L. SACCONI, 'Xth International Conferences on Coordination Chemistry, Tokyo', Plenum Press, New York, 1968, p. 95.
28. M. MASSACESI, R. PINNA, M. BIDDAU and G. PONTICELLI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, 80, 151.
29. T. N. HAZARIKA and T. BORA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 489.